

Naïve Chunking Strategies for Scalable SAS-Python Code Translation in the U.S. Census Bureau

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Abstract

Federal statistical agencies like the U.S. Census Bureau are migrating from SAS, a proprietary programming language, to open-source alternatives like Python for reduced costs. Given the size of legacy codebases, conventional machine translation strategies such as rules-based compilers or unsupervised machine translation are impractical due to burdensome manual effort or the scarcity of parallel training data for SAS and Python. This paper deploys Large Language Models (LLMs) within the constraints of federal computing environments that preclude the user of APIs or compiler feedback loops. We address two fundamental challenges: [1] designing a scalable translation pipeline that accommodates context window limitations, and [2] resolving deep structural and semantic disparities between languages. Our contributions are a modular pipeline architecture that uses naïve chunking to process large programs and a set of targeted prompt engineering and post-processing techniques. These methods successfully mitigate critical translation errors arising from differences in merging logic, row-wise vs. vectorized operations, and missing value representation, providing a practical framework for modernizing critical data infrastructure in secure environments.

Key Words: SAS, Python, LLMs, Code Translation

All views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views or policies of the U.S. Census Bureau.

1. Introduction

SAS is a proprietary programming language that has long been entrenched in federal statistical agencies and large-scale data environments. Despite its extensive capabilities, the financial burden of enterprise licensing, which can cost millions of dollars for a full implementation (FAQs, 2025), has incentivized organizations to seek cost-effective alternatives. Python, an increasingly popular open-source language, presents an attractive migration path. Python not only supports a wide array of statistical and data processing libraries, it is widely taught in academic programs making it more accessible to recent graduates. In contrast, SAS lacks the same educational ubiquity, signalling a growing skills mismatch as new talent enters Federal statistical agencies.

However, transitioning legacy codebases from SAS to Python remains a nontrivial challenge. Manual translation is time-consuming and error-prone. Traditional program translation techniques, including rules-based approaches such as Abstract Syntax Tree transformations (Albrecht et al. 1980; Veeramani, Venkatesan, and Nalinadevi 2014) and adapted neural machine translation methods (Stahlberg 2020; Lachaux et al. 2020), offer potential but require specialized infrastructure or training data. In this paper, we explore a novel alternative: using Large Language Models (LLMs) as a general-purpose mechanism for automating SAS-to-Python code translation.

To our knowledge, this work represents the first exploration of LLM-based translation from SAS to Python. We identify and address two major categories of challenges: (1) developing an effective translation pipeline that works within the constraints of LLMs, particularly regarding context window limitations and prompt engineering; and (2) resolving structural and semantic discrepancies between the two languages that can lead to translation errors. To address the first challenge, we propose a translation pipeline that employs naïve chunking strategies to facilitate translation using any LLM, regardless of its token context window. This method enables scalable translation of large codebases by splitting SAS programs into manageable segments while preserving inter-chunk

context where possible. As more capable models with larger context windows became available, we adapted the pipeline to support ingestion of entire SAS programs in a single context window when the chosen LLM supports it, avoiding chunking, simplifying the workflow, and, reducing the need for prompt continuity engineering. For the second challenge, we examine the key linguistic and operational differences between SAS and Python – such as handling of missing values (sentinel values), row-wise versus vectorized operations, and data merging semantics. We propose a combination of prompt tuning and post-processing techniques to mitigate these issues and improve translation accuracy.

2. Language-Specific Translation Challenges

2.1 Sentinel Values

A key semantic divergence between SAS and Python lies in their representations of missing values (also referred to as sentinel values). In SAS, numeric missing data can be denoted using a period (.) for general cases, and extended forms such as *.A* through *.Z* may indicate distinct types of missing values. These sentinel values are often used to encode additional context or categories within statistical workflows. For example, *.M* may be used to denote “Missing” whereas *.N* might indicate “Not in Universe” - a distinction that carries critical analytical meaning in domains like federal statistics.

Python, by contrast, provides several mechanisms for representing missing data, including the built-in *None* object, NumPy’s *np.nan*, and Pandas’ *NaN*. However, these representations are not directly analogous to SAS’s multi-type sentinel system. Python’s numerical missing values (e.g., NaN) do not support annotation or categorization, and *None* is not a valid value in numeric arrays without upcasting or introducing object types, which can degrade performance and complicate processing. As a result, one-to-one mapping between SAS and Python is not feasible using Python’s native constructs.

2.2 Row-Wise vs. Vectorized Operations

Another difference between SAS and Python lies in how they process data. SAS operates on a row-by-row basis, an approach rooted in its Program Data Vector (PDV). The PDV is a logical memory buffer that holds and processes only one record at a time. In a DATA step, the program reads a single row into the PDV, executes all relevant statements on that row’s data, writes the result, and then discards the PDV’s contents before looping to the next row. The row-wise model allows for statements like \$RETAIN\$ which instructs SAS to hold a variable’s memory across row iterations rather than resetting to missing. This is commonly used when accumulating values (e.g. running total) or carrying forward a specific value until a new one is encountered (e.g. applying a single weight to all subsequent records in a group).

In contrast, Python libraries like Pandas and Polars are built for vectorized operations. Entire datasets are loaded into memory as objects like DataFrames and calculations can be applied to whole columns. This strategy prevents one-to-one equivalents for row-iterative logic like \$RETAIN\$ without relying on explicit loops (e.g. *df.iterrows()*) that can be highly inefficient. Functional redevelopment is required to map row-wise operations to Python’s vectorized operations.

2.3 Data Merging

Merging remains another key challenge in mapping SAS to Python. SAS uses a sequential, row-by-row match-merge process on pre-sorted datasets, whereas Python uses relational, database-style joins. These distinctions become more apparent when handling duplicate keys and overlapping columns.

When duplicate keys are present, SAS pairs them sequentially (the first record from the left with the first from the right). In contrast, a standard Python join performs a cartesian product, creating a much larger dataset. Furthermore, if one dataset has fewer records for a key, SAS retains the values for any column unique to the dataset with fewer records for that key group and then propagates that

value (even if null) to the remaining rows from the other dataset for that key group. This data retention is a core feature that has no direct equivalent in Python.

Handling of overlapping (non-key) columns is another challenge. For SAS, the value from the right-most dataset overwrites the value from the left, even if that value is null. In Python however, both columns are preserved and their name updated with a suffix (e.g., column_x, column_y) to indicate their source DataFrame.

3. Translation Pipeline

Selecting an appropriate LLM for a code translation task involves balancing multiple constraints, including data security, cost, and computational resources. In contexts where sensitive data is involved, such as code governed by federal privacy regulations like Title 13, the use of locally hosted models may be mandated to ensure compliance with data handling policies. In such cases, open-source models that can be deployed on secure infrastructure offer a viable solution.

Cost is another critical consideration. Organizations with limited financial flexibility may prefer freely available or self-hosted LLMs to avoid the recurring costs associated with commercial APIs. Similarly, when hardware limitations constrain available processing power, smaller models may be favored for their reduced resource demands. Conversely, in settings where such restrictions are minimal, large-scale proprietary models – such as OpenAI’s GPT series, Google’s Gemini, or Anthropic’s Claude – can be leveraged for their superior performance and advanced capabilities.

The choice of model has direct implications for translation architecture, particularly with respect to token context limits. Models with smaller context windows necessitate chunking strategies to divide code into manageable segments for translation. The next section outlines our approach to constructing a naive chunking pipeline designed to accommodate models with limited context capacity. The pipeline is model-agnostic, enabling its use with any LLM regardless of token capacity. While this strategy introduces some limitations, particularly with respect to maintaining global program context, it provides a scalable method for translation under strict token constraints.

Figure 1: Limited Context Window Pipeline

3.1 Limited Context Window Approach

3.1.1 Parsing

Raw SAS programs are parsed by line into multiple categories for targeted translation in future steps: single-line comments, multi-line comments, steps (data, proc), macros, and additional loose code (e.g. libname statements). Stored in a JSON file, each category is associated with start and stop line numbers, labels, and token counts.

3.1.2 Rules-Based Conversions

Prior to LLM translation, it is effective to control for areas of the code that are tedious, where LLM models are likely to default to pseudocode or comments suggesting where a user might continue the translation manually. Common examples of this are array instantiations in SAS, where a list with the name of each variable is made explicit, accumulating as many as hundreds of lines in some programs. Here, we apply rules-based conversions to convert these into Python and re-index within the JSON to mark them as already translated.

```
DATA output;
  SET input;

  ARRAY arr_A {*} varA varB varC varD varE
  ARRAY arr_B {*} varA varB varC varD varE
  ARRAY arr_C {*} varA varB varC varD varE
  ARRAY arr_D {*} varA varB varC varD varE
  ARRAY arr_E {*} varA varB varC varD varE

  /* Dependencies */
  %INCLUDE "path/to/dependencies.sas";
  %INCLUDE "path/to/more_dependencies.txt";

RUN;
```

Figure 2: SAS code that would be identified by rules-based conversions

3.1.3 Chunking

Chunking is applied within SAS steps, where lines of code can range from as little as three to thousands. Naïve chunking looks for the first line break after 10 lines of code, ending the current chunk and reindexing in the JSON file. Several strategies were applied in early sampling, ranging from varied line counts, line counts derived from the maximum token count of the LLM, and token counts themselves. An effective strategy has been to assume line breaks introduced by the programs' creators were written for the purpose of designating a natural end and beginning in logic. Therefore, a loop or set of nested conditions wouldn't be separated by our chunking strategy. Figure 2 displays a possible outcome from this approach, where the strategy is to keep specific operations associated with one another together: macros, if-then logic, loops, dependencies, merging operations. One drawback in this approach is programs written by developers where line breaks were not introduced—something observed in our experimentation. Here, our regrouping strategy is decided for us on the developers' part. Another possibility would be line breaks introduced within portions of code by accident or for the purposes of specifying a comment. Here, our strategy also fails to consider that possibility, but grouping aims to resolve this in the next phase of the pipeline.

3.1.4 Grouping

Grouping takes a series of chunks and combines them to expand the amount of information available to the LLM for translation. Given a maximum token limit minus the token count of the prompt, we reach a token amount that the group attempts to approach when adding chunks.

3.1.5 Prompting

Fortunately, early sampling proved retrieval augmented generation (RAG) approaches effective where SAS or Python documentation was not necessary for generating high quality translations. However, prompting for specific strategies in package use, architecture, and more were notably helpful in delivering better results.

```
Role setting (i.e. you are an expert in SAS)

Your task:
1. Step 1
2. Step 2
3. Step 3

Instructions for interpreting SAS:
- Intepret logic this way
- Ignore these
- Understand this and the equivalent in Python

Instructions for Python implementation:
- Apply this approach when necessary
- Use library X for Y
- Functions vs. methods
- Redevelop loops for vectorized operations

Here is the SAS code for translation
{sas_chunk}

Here are the Python variables declared in previous translations:
{python_vars}
```

Figure 3: Example prompt language

3.1.6 Translation-Documentation Loop

To preserve context across isolated groups, we utilize a translation-documentation loop where translation t is passed through a documentation pipeline where another language model extracts useful descriptions of each variable, dataset, and other artifacts and stores them in a JSON that is passed into the prompt for group $t-1$. This mechanism ensures the translation model is not reproducing redundant code, and makes use of information available in previous translations for coherence. The translation-documentation loop is performed on each group, producing a n number of translations t .

3.1.7 Post-Processing

Post-processing includes relocating all package imports to the top of the translation, inserting any leftover comments or documentation from the SAS program relating to the history or purpose of that original program, pruning any syntax or semantic errors, and then applying pep8 formatting for readability. After each translated chunk has gone through these steps, they are stitched back together to form one coherent translation for last-mile efforts.

3.2 Full-Context Approach

When working with models that support large context windows, the need for chunking diminishes. In these cases, the entire SAS program can be provided as input in a single prompt, significantly simplifying the translation pipeline. By adjusting the pipeline to leverage large-context models when available, we can reduce engineering complexity and improve both efficiency and translation quality. For this paper, we rely on Google’s Gemini 1.5 Pro.

3.2.1 Prompting

Prompting follows a similar strategy to the limited-context strategy, with a few exceptions. While the maximum input token size is 1,048,576 tokens, the maximum output token size is only 8,192. For each consecutive pass over a SAS program, the previously generated content is passed as context along with the SAS program to allow the model to continue translating. When the translation is

complete, we prompt the model to indicate it has finished by ending the generated sequence with “ENDED TRANSLATION”.

4. Findings

4.1 Strategies for Mitigating Language-Specific Translation Challenges

4.1.1 Sentinel Values

To address the semantic mismatch between SAS’s nuanced missing value system and Python’s limited native representations, we adopted two primary strategies: flag columns and value mappings. In the flag column approach, missing values in the SAS dataset are translated to a common Python representation (e.g., *None*), while a supplementary boolean or categorical flag column is added to indicate the specific type of missingness originally encoded in SAS (e.g., *.M* or *.N*). This preserves semantic fidelity while maintaining data type consistency across the original column. In the value mapping approach, each SAS sentinel value is mapped to a unique placeholder that does not exist in the domain of valid values for the dataset. For example, *.N* may be mapped to -9999999 and *.M* to -9999991 . These values are substituted in place of the original sentinel values during translation and cast to match the column’s data type. This approach allows for direct numerical computations without schema modification but requires careful downstream interpretation.

The choice between these approaches depends on several factors: (1) whether there exist safe placeholder values that do not conflict with the domain of the original data; (2) whether the dataset size and structure can accommodate additional flag columns without significant performance degradation; (3) the needs of subject-matter experts and their expectations for interpreting missingness in downstream workflows. To operationalize these strategies during translation, we experimented with prompting LLMs to implement the desired handling technique. By clearly describing the selected approach within the prompt, we found the LLMs typically generated valid substitutions for simple assignments. However, issues frequently arose in conditional logic or arithmetic expressions involving these values.

Consider the following SAS example:

```
SAS


---


%if VarA ne 1 then VarB=.N;
%if VarC < 0 then VarD=VarC * 100;
```

Figure 4: Sample SAS Code

Assuming the *.N* value is mapped to -9999999 , a typical LLM-generated translation might be:

```
Python


---


if VarA != 1:
    VarB = -9999999
if VarC < 0:
    VarD = VarC * 100
```

Figure 5: Typical LLM Python translation

While syntactically valid, this translation fails to preserve the original SAS behavior. In SAS, missing values propagate through arithmetic operations, so $\text{VarC} * 100$ would yield a missing value if VarC were *.M* or *.N*. In contrast, in the Python translation, $\text{VarC} * 100$ would produce a

large negative number, which potentially could contaminate downstream analysis. A more semantically faithful translation would explicitly exclude placeholder values from computation:

```
Python
if VarC < 0 and VarC not in [-9999999,
-9999991]:
    VarD = VarC * 100
```

Figure 6: More faithful Python translation

These kinds of subtle distinctions can introduce substantial discrepancies in output datasets if not addressed. Consequently, post-processing remains essential for validating and correcting translations, particularly in complex logical conditions or statistical operations involving missing values.

4.1.2 Row-Wise Versus Vectorized Operations

Our primary method for preventing inefficient, row-wise translations was to prompt the LLM to favor vectorized solutions over row-wise translations. Below are examples of simple, conditional SAS logic where the LLM implemented ideal vectorized approaches. Figures 7 and 8 display the use of NumPy's select approach, rather than iterating over the rows of the DataFrame and using if-else logic.

```
SAS
IF age >= 65 THEN age_group = 'Senior';
ELSE IF age >= 18 THEN age_group =
'Adult';
ELSE age_group = 'Minor';
```

Figure 7: if-else SAS code

```
Python
# Define the conditions and the
corresponding choices
conditions = [new['age'] >= 65,
new['age'] >= 1]
choices = ['Senior', 'Adult']

# numpy.select is a vectorized way to
replicate the SAS code
new['age_group'] =
np.select(conditions, choices,
default='Minor')
```

Figure 8: Python vectorized translation

Figures 9 and 10 display an approach where if-else logic is structured as a dictionary in Python that is applied to a column with the map method:

```

SAS
-----
IF mycode IN (8,24,43) THEN
  DO;
    newcode=1;
  END;
ELSE IF mycode IN (33,35,41) THEN
  DO;
    newcode=2;
  END;
ELSE /* ... and so on ... */

```

Figure 9: if-else SAS code

```

Python
-----
# Mapping is defined as a dictionary
CODE_MAPPING = {
  8: 1, 24: 1, 43: 1, # Group 1
  33: 2, 35: 2, 41: 2, # Group 2
  # etc ...          # Group 3
}

# The mapping is applied to the whole
# column in one operation.
df['newcode'] = \
  df['mycode'].map(CODE_MAPPING)

```

Figure 10: Python vectorized translation

While such prompting was successful for simple, conditional SAS logic, this approach can fall short in the case of more complex, stateful operations. The SAS retain statement which carries a variable's value from a previous row to the current one exemplifies this issue. For such a case, the LLM must understand the intent of the SAS operation to generate a semantically equivalent vectorized solution using for example, groupby and a window function like cumsum() or ffill(). In our experience, LLMs often failed to make this translation, illustrating that even with targeted prompting, manual intervention has been essential for translating complex, stateful SAS logic. Below is an example of such a stateful operation.

```

SAS
-----
DATA customer_cumulative_sales;
  SET sorted_sales;
  BY customer_id;
  RETAIN running_total 0;
  IF FIRST.customer_id THEN
    running_total=0;
    running_total=running_total +
  sale_amount;
RUN;

```

Figure 11: stateful SAS code using RETAIN

```

Python
-----
# The groupby().cumsum() pattern is
# the direct vectorized equivalent.
df['running_total'] = \
  df.groupby('customer_id') \
    ['sale_amount'].cumsum()

```

Figure 12: Python translation of SAS stateful code

And in some cases, the SAS logic is too complex to be vectorized. These cases typically involved intricate multi-step calculations such as string manipulation, conditional loops, or functions that operate on individual digits of a number. An LLM may struggle to translate this either by attempting to create a convoluted and incorrect vectorized approach or by producing an inefficient row-wise loop. Often, the best solution in these situations is to capture the procedural logic in a function that is then applied to each row.

```

SAS
DATA validated_products;
  SET product_source;

  *** Logic operates on individual
  *** digits of the serial number
  acct_str = put(base_serial_num,
12.);
  running_sum = 0;

  *** Loop through the number,
  *** applying a different weight to
  *** each position
  DO i = 1 to length(acct_str);
    digit = input(substr(acct_str,
                        i, 1), 1.);

    *** Different logic for odd
    *** and even positions
    IF mod(i, 2) = 1 THEN DO;
      product = digit * 3;
      running_sum = running_sum
        + floor(product / 10)
        + mod(product, 10);
    END;
    ELSE DO;
      running_sum = running_sum
        + digit;
    END;
  END;

  *** The final check digit is
  *** derived from the sum
  validation_digit = mod(10 -
    mod(running_sum, 10), 10);
RUN
;

```

Figure 13: Complex SAS code

```

Python
def calc_validation_digit(serial_num):
    """
    Calculates a validation digit based
    on a custom weighting algorithm.
    """
    if pd.isna(serial_num):
        return None

    s = str(int(serial_num))
    running_sum = 0

    for i, digit_char in enumerate(s):
        digit = int(digit_char)
        # Apply different logic for
        # odd/even positions
        if i % 2 == 0:
            # Corresponds to odd
            # positions in SAS (1-
            # based)
            product = digit * 3
            running_sum += \
                (product // 10) \
                + (product % 10)
        else:
            # Corresponds to even
            # positions in SAS
            running_sum += digit

    return (10 - (running_sum %
    10)) % 10

# Apply the function row-wise using
# .apply() and a lambda function.
df['validation_digit'] =
df['base_serial_num'].apply(lambda num:
    calculate_validation_digit(num))

```

Figure 14: Python translation that maintains row-wise approach

4.1.3 Data Merging

To address the challenges of replicating SAS MERGE, we developed a custom Python function that emulates SAS's logic using a multi-step, vectorized approach. First, to mimic SAS's sequential pairing and avoid a Cartesian product, the function assigns a unique sequence number to each record within its key group. By joining on this sequence number and the original keys, it correctly pairs records one-to-one. The function correctly handles non-key, overlapping columns (i.e., columns with the same name across datasets) by implementing SAS's strict overwrite rule, ensuring the value from the right-hand dataset is used, even if the value is null. Finally, the function accurately manages scenarios where one dataset has more records for a key than the other. For overlapping columns, values for the excess rows are simply taken from the longer dataset. However, for columns that exist only in the dataset with fewer records for the key group, the function replicates SAS's data retention by capturing the value (even if it is null) from the last paired row for that key group and propagates that value to all the remaining, unpaired rows from the longer dataset. This approach ensures fidelity to the SAS merge while leveraging the performance of vectorized operations. The full function can be found in Appendix A.

4.2 Comparison of Pipeline Performance

We applied our translation pipeline to four proprietary, real-world SAS codebases, with a total of 150 SAS programs. Two of these codebases followed a linear structure, wherein datasets were processed sequentially across scripts. The other two were modularized; they leveraged macros across SAS files and exhibited more complex control flows and outputs.

Table 1: Translated Codebases Overview

Codebase	Architecture	Program Count
A	Linear	41
B	Linear	50
C	Modularized	24
D	Modularized	35

4.2.1 Limited Context Window Approach

The limited context window approach enabled scalable translation of large SAS programs using models with limited context windows. Providing context about previous code chunks within later prompts moderately mitigated issues of variable and macro reference loss. Nonetheless, inter-chunk coherence remained an issue. LLMs frequently failed to maintain awareness of previously defined variables, temporary datasets, and function outputs. Variables introduced earlier in the code were often “forgotten”, even when a list a previously defined variables was provided within the prompt. This led to syntax errors that needed to be corrected prior to being able to run the code. The approach also fell prey to language-specific translation challenges outlined in section 3.

4.2.2 Full Context Approach

With the emergence of LLMs supporting extended context windows, we evaluated full-program translation. This approach maintained continuity of variable names and control structures across the entire translation. There were fewer instances of syntax errors or lost context compared to the chunking method. However, the approach still exhibited translation inaccuracies associated with the language-specific translation challenges identified in section 3. Additionally, modularized codebases still presented contextual challenges for this approach because of the limited amount of context that can be passed to prompts about dependency and caller programs. This strategy showed clear advantages in reducing context-related errors but still required review to ensure semantic alignment with the original SAS logic.

Table 2: Approach Comparison Summary

Dimension	Limited Context Window/Chunking Approach	Full-Context Strategy
Context Retention	Partial with manual augmentation	High with natural retention
Syntax Accuracy	Moderate and more prone to issues	Higher
Flexibility Across Code	Scalable for all sizes of programs	Limited by model context window
Suitability for Modular Code	Challenging	Challenging
Post-Processing Effort	High	Moderate

4.2.3 Comparing Limited Context and Full Context Approaches

To illustrate the differences in translation quality between the limited context and full context approaches, we can compare their outputs on specific translation tasks. Both approaches proved capable of accurately translating self-contained, low-context SAS operations, such as getting

environment variables, basic data manipulation with a single DATA step, or standard procedures like PROC SORT. However, when the translation depends on information defined much earlier in the program, like custom macro variables or the schema of an intermediary dataset, the advantage of the full-context approach becomes evident. The following examples compare the outputs from both approaches, highlighting where the full-context method provided a more robust and functionally accurate translation. For each example below, a snippet of SAS code is provided followed by the limited context Python translation and the full context Python translation displayed side by side.

The below example illustrates how the limited context approach correctly translated the SAS code but used a row-wise solution whereas the full context translation used a vectorized approach.

```
SAS
-----
IF gestfips IN (9,23,25,33,44,50) THEN
  DO;
    gedit=1;
  END;
ELSE IF gestfips IN (34,36,42) THEN
  DO;
    gedit=2;
```

Figure 15: SAS code used as source code for following Python translations

Both translations below are functionality correct, but the full context translation provided a more optimal, vectorized solution.

```
Limited Context Python Translation
-----
def transform_row(row):
    #... (other assignments)
    gestfips = row['GESTFIPS']
    if gestfips in [9, 23, 25, 33, 44,
50]:
        row['GEDIV'] = 1
    elif gestfips in [34, 36, 42]:
        row['GEDIV'] = 2
    # ... (etc.) ...
    else:
        row['GEDIV'] = None
    #...
    return row

# The function is called for every row
df = df.apply(transform_row, axis=1)
```

Figure 16: Limited context Python translation provides a row-wise approach

```
Full Context Python Translation
-----
# Recode GESTFIPS to GEDIV
conditions_gediv = [
    ucf['GESTFIPS'].isin([9, 23, 25,
33, 44, 50]),
    ucf['GESTFIPS'].isin([34, 36, 42]),
    # ... (etc.) ...
    ucf['GESTFIPS'].isin([2, 6, 15, 41,
53])
]
choices_gediv = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7,
8, 9]
ucf['GEDIV'] =
np.select(conditions_gediv,
choices_gediv, default=np.nan)
```

Figure 17: Full context Python translation provides a vectorized approach

The following example illustrates how the limited context translation can miss crucial logic when translating significant amounts of code.

```
SAS
-----
DATA outds.ucf outds.&mmm&yy.newids(KEEP=ctrlnum);
/* many more lines of code */
IF (newflg eq 1) THEN
DO;
    output outds.&mmm&yy.newids;
END;
```

Figure 18: SAS code used as source code for following Python translations

Because the output statement for the newids dataset appears so much later in the SAS code, the limited context window does not track that the dataset should be subset to only records where the newflg column is equal to one. The full context translation did capture this conditional logic.

```
Limited context Python translation
-----
# --- Create outds.&mmm&yy.newids ---
newids = ucf[['CTRLNUM']]

# Define output path and save transids dataset
newids_output_path =
os.path.join(sas_dir_path,
f'{mmm}{yy}newids.parquet')
newids_df.to_parquet(newids_output_path
, index=False)
```

Figure 19: Limited context Python translation fails to capture SAS' conditional output logic

```
Full context Python translation
-----
# Create NEWIDS DataFrame
newids = ucf.loc[ucf['NEWFLG'] == 1,
['CTRLNUM']].copy()

# Save the newids dataset
newids.to_parquet(newids_output_path,
index=False)
```

Figure 20: Full context Python translation fails to capture SAS' conditional output logic

This final example demonstrates how the limited-context approach can fail when a dataset's origin is not within the immediate prompt. The chunked translation incorrectly assumes a dataset is available for input, whereas the full-context translation correctly recognizes it as the output of an earlier merge. identified.

```
SAS
-----
DATA outds.ucfwcfhh(DROP=gewcf ucfnmtch cpsmat);
MERGE hhdoutds (IN=a) ucfoutds (IN=b) END=eof;
BY ctrlnum;
```

Figure 21: SAS code used as source code for following Python translations

The full context translation correctly performs the merge to create the dataset, but manual intervention was still needed in this case because the data contained duplicate keys, requiring the use of the replicate_sas_merge_pandas function discussed in section 4.1.3 and listed in appendix A.

Limited context Python translation

```
# Define filepath for ucwcfhh dataset
ucwcfhh_path =
os.path.join(sas_dir_path,
f'{mmm}{yy}ucwcfhh.parquet')

# Read the dataset
ucwcfhh_df =
pd.read_parquet(ucwcfhh_path)
```

Figure 22: Limited context Python translation tries to read a dataset it should create

Full context Python translation

```
# Merge hhdoutds and ucfoutds
merged_df = pd.merge(hhdoutds,
ucfoutds, on='CTRLNUM', how='outer',
indicator=True)

# The final dataset UCFWCFHH contains
only matched records
ucwcfhh =
matched_records.drop(columns=['_merge']
)
```

Figure 23: Full context Python translation correctly creates the dataset

5. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper has explored an LLM-assisted methodology for translating codebases from SAS to Python, addressing the unique syntactic and semantic challenges inherent in such cross-language translation. We examined key language-specific issues, such as the handling of sentinel values, distinctions between row-wise and vectorized operations, and the complexities of data merging, and demonstrated how LLMs can assist in overcoming them through carefully designed prompting strategies.

We introduced and evaluated two distinct translation pipelines. The Limited Context Window pipeline, which relies on naive chunking to accommodate model token limits, was found to be scalable across codebases sizes but prone to syntactic inconsistencies and required significant manual post-processing to preserve context across chunks. In contrast, the Full Context Window pipeline leveraged LLMs with large maximum token limits to process entire scripts without chunking. While this approach naturally retained context and improved syntax fidelity, it remained constrained by the model's maximum input token length and faced difficulties with modularized code structures. Both approaches necessitated post-processing, although to varying degrees, highlighting the continued need for human oversight in production-level code translation. Prompt engineering emerged as a critical factor in translation quality, especially when guiding LLMs through language-specific challenges.

For future work, the integration of retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) techniques holds promise for further improving translation outcomes. By drawing on external sources such as SAS documentation or previously translated patterns, RAG could enable more nuanced, context-aware translations, particularly in areas such as nested conditional logic, PROC statement conversions, and complex data merges. For especially intricate or large-scale codebases, future research may explore the viability of graph-based representations of SAS programs, facilitating more structured indexing and reconstruction processes during translation. Ultimately, this work lays a foundation for automating legacy code migration through LLMs, and invites further innovation at the intersection of software engineering, natural language processing, and human-computer collaboration.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Custom Python Function for SAS Merge Replication

The following Python function, `replicate_sas_merge_pandas`, is designed to emulate the sequential processing logic of the SAS MERGE statement, correctly handling many-to-many joins and the overwrite behavior of overlapping columns.

Listing A.1: The `replicate_sas_merge_pandas` function (Continues on next page):

Python

```
def replicate_sas_merge_pandas(
    left_df: pd.DataFrame,
    right_df: pd.DataFrame,
    on: List[str],
    how: str,
    logger: logging.Logger
) -> pd.DataFrame:
    """
    Replicates the SAS MERGE behavior for many-to-many joins using pandas.
    - For overlapping columns, take right value when right row exists (even if null).
    - For non-overlapping columns, propagates the last known value (including nulls)
      from the source dataframe within a key group.
    - Assumes data is pre-sorted to match SAS sort
    """
    logger.info(f"Performing pandas SAS-style '{how}' merge on keys: {on}")
    # Create copies to avoid modifying original DataFrames
    left_df = left_df.copy()
    right_df = right_df.copy()
    # --- Step 1: Keep track of original unique keys for final filtering ---
    keys_to_keep = None
    if how == 'left':
        keys_to_keep = left_df[on].drop_duplicates()
    elif how == 'inner':
        left_keys = left_df[on].drop_duplicates()
        right_keys = right_df[on].drop_duplicates()
        # The 'inner' merge of unique keys gets the set of keys to keep
        keys_to_keep = pd.merge(left_keys, right_keys, on=on, how='inner')
    # --- Step 2: Create temporary row numbers (cumcount is 0-based, so add 1) ---
    merge_idx_col = "_merge_idx"
    left_df[merge_idx_col] = left_df.groupby(on).cumcount() + 1
    right_df[merge_idx_col] = right_df.groupby(on).cumcount() + 1
    # --- Step 2.5: Track max merge_idx per key group ---
    max_left_idx = "_max_left_idx"
    left_max_df = left_df.groupby(on, as_index=False).agg({merge_idx_col:
'max'}).rename(columns={merge_idx_col: max_left_idx})
    max_right_idx = "_max_right_idx"
    right_max_df = right_df.groupby(on, as_index=False).agg({merge_idx_col:
'max'}).rename(columns={merge_idx_col: max_right_idx})
    # --- Step 3: Add indicator column ---
    right_indicator = "_from_right"
    right_df[right_indicator] = 1
```

Listing A.1: The replicate_sas_merge_pandas function (Continued from previous page):

Python

```
# --- Step 4: Identify and rename overlapping columns ---
left_cols = set(left_df.columns) - {merge_idx_col}
right_cols = set(right_df.columns) - {right_indicator, merge_idx_col}
on_keys = set(on)
overlapping_cols = list((left_cols & right_cols) - on_keys)
left_only_cols = list(left_cols - right_cols - on_keys)
right_only_cols = list(right_cols - left_cols - on_keys)
right_rename_map = {col: f"{col}_right" for col in overlapping_cols}
if overlapping_cols:
    logger.info(f"SAS Merge: Found {len(overlapping_cols)} overlapping columns")
    right_df = right_df.rename(columns=right_rename_map)
# --- Step 5: Perform the full outer join ---
merged_df = pd.merge(
    left_df,
    right_df,
    on=on + [merge_idx_col],
    how='outer'
)
# --- Step 6: Add max index information ---
merged_df = pd.merge(merged_df, left_max_df, on=on, how='left')
merged_df = pd.merge(merged_df, right_max_df, on=on, how='left')
# --- Step 7: Sort by keys and row number ---
merged_df = merged_df.sort_values(by=on + [merge_idx_col]).reset_index(drop=True)
# --- Step 8: Handle overlapping columns using SAS logic ---
for col in overlapping_cols:
    right_col = f"{col}_right"
    # Use numpy.where for conditional selection
    merged_df[col] = np.where(
        merged_df[right_indicator] == 1,
        merged_df[right_col], # Use right value (even if null)
        merged_df[col]       # Otherwise, use left value
    )
merged_df = merged_df.drop(columns=[right_col])
```

Listing A.1: The replicate_sas_merge_pandas function (Continued from previous page):

Python

```
# --- Step 9: - Handle left-only columns ---
if left_only_cols:
    for col in left_only_cols:
        prop_col_name = f"_{col}_prop"
        # Create a map of {key -> last_value}
        prop_map = merged_df[merged_df[merge_idx_col] ==
merged_df[max_left_idx]][on + [col]]
        prop_map = prop_map.rename(columns={col: prop_col_name})
        # Merge the propagation value back to the main df
        merged_df = pd.merge(merged_df, prop_map, on=on, how='left')
        # Apply the propagation value conditionally
        merged_df[col] = np.where(
            merged_df[merge_idx_col] <= merged_df[max_left_idx],
            merged_df[col],
            merged_df[prop_col_name]
        )
        # Clean up the temporary propagation column
        merged_df = merged_df.drop(columns=[prop_col_name])
# --- Step 10: - Handle right-only columns ---
if right_only_cols:
    for col in right_only_cols:
        prop_col_name = f"_{col}_prop"
        # Create a map of {key -> last_value}
        prop_map = merged_df[merged_df[merge_idx_col] ==
merged_df[max_right_idx]][on + [col]]
        prop_map = prop_map.rename(columns={col: prop_col_name})
        # Merge the propagation value back to the main df
        merged_df = pd.merge(merged_df, prop_map, on=on, how='left')
        # Apply the propagation value conditionally
        merged_df[col] = np.where(
            merged_df[merge_idx_col] <= merged_df[max_right_idx],
            merged_df[col],
            merged_df[prop_col_name]
        )
        # Clean up the temporary propagation column
        merged_df = merged_df.drop(columns=[prop_col_name])
# --- Step 11: Filter the result based on join type ---
if how in ('left', 'inner'):
    # An inner merge with the unique keys effectively filters the merged result
    merged_df = pd.merge(merged_df, keys_to_keep, on=on, how='inner')
# --- Step 12: Clean up temporary columns ---
cols_to_drop = [merge_idx_col, right_indicator, max_left_idx, max_right_idx]
merged_df = merged_df.drop(columns=cols_to_drop, errors='ignore')

return merged_df
```